

EXPLORING CURATION STRATEGIES FOR AN OPEN WEB INDEX

F. Douglas[†], S. Krol, Hochschule der Medien, Stuttgart, Germany

Abstract

This project, conducted by a student group from Stuttgart Media University in collaboration with the Open Search Foundation, investigated various aspects of curating an Open Web Index. The primary goal was to explore methods for organizing, maintaining and ensuring the quality of web content.

The project focused on two main areas: content organization and thematic structuring, and the development of a transparent and participatory rating model for web resources. The team reviewed historically developed methods of information organization from information science, as well as existing classification systems and metadata schemes, such as Dewey Decimal Classification, Universal Decimal Classification, Dublin Core, and Schema, to evaluate their applicability for an OWI.

To address scalability, both supervised and unsupervised machine learning techniques were considered as methods for classifying and structuring web content dynamically and efficiently.

The proposed rating model aimed to ensure the quality and trustworthiness of indexed content. It included gamification elements to motivate user participation, such as badges, levels, and quests. The model featured a community-driven approach with user authentication and majority decision mechanisms to prevent misuse and ensure balanced perspectives. Additionally, the model incorporated a detailed rating interface that guided users through evaluating websites based on criteria like content quality, language, usability, trustworthiness, accuracy, and accessibility. Feedback mechanisms and reporting options were included to continuously improve the platform and address any violations or issues.

The project also researched the role of social annotation in enriching metadata and promoting transparency.

This study contributes insights into the curation of an Open Web Index, highlighting the integration of traditional information science techniques with modern, scalable and community-driven methods.

[†] fd051@hdm-stuttgart.de